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THE PLACE OF DIGITALISATION IN THE RURAL AREAS DEVELOPMENT OF UKRAINE

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Abstract: The article analyses the role of digitalisation in the development of rural areas in Ukraine. In particular, the main documents aimed at digital transformation and digitalisation of rural areas are studied, including the EU-Ukraine Association, the State Strategy for Regional Development, the Economic Strategy, as well as ministerial plans. It is established that the process of digital transformation of rural areas of Ukraine has faced a number of important challenges, such as insufficient funding and resistance from society. Decentralization has increased the responsibility of communities for their own development, but limited budgetary resources often hinder the implementation of digital initiatives. In addition, many residents are afraid or reluctant to adopt new technologies, which is exacerbated by limited access to technical knowledge and low technical capacity in communities. It is emphasized that these challenges need to be addressed immediately, as digital transformation plays a key role in the development of rural communities and is an important factor in their future success.

Key words: digitalisation, decentralization, reform, rural areas, territorial community, digitalisation, digital transformation.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada Ukrainada qishloq hududlarini rivojlantirishda raqamlashtirishning roli tahlil qilinadi. Xususan, qishloq hududlarini raqamli o'zgartirish va raqamlashtirishga qaratilgan asosiy hujjatlar, jumladan, "Yevropa Ittifoqi – Ukraina" assotsiatsiyasi, Mintaqaviy rivojlanish bo'yicha Davlat strategiyasi, Iqtisodiy strategiya, shuningdek, vazirlik rejalari o'rganilmoqda. Aniqlanishicha, Ukrainaning qishloq joylarini raqamli o'zgartirish jarayoni moliyalashtirishning yetarli emasligi va jamiyatning qarshiligi kabi bir qator muhim muammolarga duch kelgan. Markazsizlashtirish jamoalarning o'z rivojlanishi uchun mas'uliyatini oshirdi, ammo cheklangan budjet resurslari ko'pincha raqamli tashabbuslarni amalga oshirishga to'sqinlik qiladi. Bundan tashqari, ko'plab aholi yangi texnologiyalarni qo'llashdan qo'rqishadi yoki istamaydilar, bu esa jamoalarda texnik bilimlarga kirishning cheklanganligi va texnik imkoniyatlarning pastligi bilan kuchayadi. Bu vazifalarni zudlik bilan hal etish zarurligi, chunki raqamli transformatsiya qishloq aholi punktlari rivojida muhim o'rin tutishi hamda ularning kelajakdagi muvaffaqiyatlarida muhim omil bo'layotgani ta'kidlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamlashtirish, markazsizlashtirish, islohot, qishloq joylari, hududiy hamjamiyat, raqamlashtirish, raqamli transformatsiya.

Аннотация: Абстрактный. В статье анализируется роль цифровизации в развитии сельских территорий Украины. В частности, изучаются основные документы, направленные на цифровую трансформацию и цифровизацию села, в том числе Ассоциация ЕС-Украина, Государственную стратегию регионального развития, Экономическую стратегию, а также министерские планы. Установлено, что процесс цифровой трансформации сельских территорий Украины столкнулся с рядом важных проблем, таких как недостаточное финансирование и сопротивление со стороны общества. Децентрализация повысила ответственность сообществ за собственное развитие, однако ограниченность бюджетных ресурсов зачастую препятствует реализации цифровых инициатив. Кроме того, многие жители боятся или не хотят внедрять новые технологии, что усугубляется ограниченным доступом к техническим знаниям и низким техническим потенциалом в сообществах. Подчеркивается, что эти проблемы необходимо решать незамедлительно, поскольку цифровая трансформация играет ключевую роль в развитии сельских сообществ и является важным фактором их будущего успеха.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация, децентрализация, реформа, сельская местность, территориальная община, цифровизация, цифровая трансформация.

Rural areas play a key role in the development of the national economy of Ukraine and its regions: ensuring food security, production of environmentally friendly products and use of natural, human and economic resources. An important task is to overcome or at least reduce the differential development of different

territories at the regional and national levels. Unpredictable circumstances, in particular in the context of military conflict, emphasize the need to develop conceptual approaches to ensure balanced development of rural areas for the long term, with the possibility of adjusting certain aspects in real time.

In 2014, Ukraine launched a decentralization reform aimed at creating capable territorial communities through the transfer of significant powers and resources from state authorities to local governments. Under these conditions, the role of local self-government communities in the country's socio-economic development is growing.

The administrative-territorial structure of Ukraine includes 27833 settlements, which, according to the decentralisation reform, are united into 1469 territorial communities, 409 of which are urban, 435 are rural and 625 are villages. The more convenient it is for residents to communicate with the community leadership, the more effective management decisions are made. This was important before the full-scale invasion, and now it is becoming a key aspect of joint work between the leadership and residents of the community^[2, 3]. In modern conditions, digitalization is the key to creating an open attitude of the community to its residents, i.e. establishing two-way communication between the community leadership and its residents, understanding their needs and requests, and finding the best ways to address them in the first place. And while there have been significant developments in this direction in cities, in rural areas such communication is quite problematic^[4].

Not all experts agree with the need for urgent digital transformation, arguing that now is not the right time for it and that we should focus on rebuilding destroyed housing, roads and institutions. However, in our opinion, now is the most appropriate time to actively digitize communities, especially in the context of rebuilding.

In the context of the military conflict and under the influence of decentralization processes in rural areas, it is important to develop integrated approaches to interaction between the authorities, communities and stakeholders. This enables the latter to make important decisions at the local level, in particular within territorial communities, where each community can make its own offers for solving rural development problems. At the same time, the decentralization process of territorial communities gives them significant powers to allocate additional resources that come to local budgets in connection with decentralization.

In the context of territorial community development, digitalisation is not limited to service delivery today. It contributes to the strategic development of the community, in particular, a comprehensive plan for the restoration and development of each community should be justified logically and transparently, based on the analysis of specific data, and the community, in turn, should be able to collect and adequately evaluate this data, even if it is partially digitalised.

It is important to note that the government of Ukraine was active in the context of digital transformation and digitalisation of the regions even before February 2022, i.e. before the full-scale invasion. For example, the transfer of public services online and the digitalisation of processes were planned as part of the EU-Ukraine Association Agreement^[1], the State Strategy for Regional Development^[7], the Economic Strategy^[8], and ministerial plans. Many Ukrainians have already had the opportunity to evaluate the work of the "Diia" portal and the convenience of Administrative Service Centres (ASCs).

However, it is worth noting that the process of digital transformation is slow and the reason for this is two very important aspects: first of all, it is insufficient funding, which hinders the introduction of new electronic services. Decentralization requires communities to rely mainly on their own budgets, and often funds for such services are allocated on a residual basis. The next significant factor in this process is the reluctance or fear of change by the vast majority of society, which is exacerbated by the low level of technical and intellectual capacity of many communities. Many residents believe that they do not have enough money to purchase new equipment, and that there are no vacancies for technical specialists. They may also face difficulties in attracting external specialists due to lack of funds or inability to compete with market conditions. However, these challenges need to be addressed urgently, as digital transformation plays a key role in the development of communities and is an important component of their future success.

The State Strategy for Regional Development for 2021-2027 defines rural development as one of the operational goals, and digitalisation is defined as one of the key aspects of many tasks to achieve this goal. Thus, one of the tasks is to stimulate the development of information and communication technologies in rural areas, in particular, to ensure that 100% of rural areas are covered by fixed broadband Internet access and 95% of the population by mobile Internet to enable the formation of new interregional connections. The task of stimulating the small and medium-sized enterprises development in rural areas is also envisaged with the use of digital technologies, including providing accessible entrepreneurship training in online, offline and blended learning formats, as well as expanding the network of entrepreneurship support centers "Diia. Business". The Strategy pays considerable attention to the healthcare sector, which is impossible without ensuring that healthcare facilities are properly equipped, including broadband Internet access and modern hardware, information and software tools for the functioning of the electronic healthcare system. Other very important tasks for the development of rural areas in the context of digitalisation are the full computerisation of general secondary

education institutions with the involvement of various sources of funding, digital literacy training for teachers, and raising the level of digital literacy of the rural population, in particular through the implementation of the project “Diia. Digital education” [8].

On 18 July 2023, the Government approved the Procedure for the Development, Implementation and Monitoring of the Plan for the Restoration and Development of Regions and Territorial Communities, developed by the Ministry of Communities, Territories and Infrastructure. The document states that the monitoring of the plan implementation for the restoration and development of regions may be carried out, including the use of the Unified Digital Integrated Information and Analytical System for the Management of the Process of Reconstruction of Real Estate and Infrastructure, as well as the Information and Telecommunication System – a unified geographic information system for monitoring and evaluating the development of regions and territorial communities after its implementation [9].

In this case, digitalisation plays the role of a transparency tool in the recovery of communities and Ukraine as a whole. This is important to international donors who are already providing financial support to the state and to themselves. And, hopefully, this will reduce internal resistance on the part of the leadership (which is based, among other things, on a lack of future benefits understanding). Despite other priorities, the Ministry of Digital Transformation continues to support councils. Attention to the issues and challenges of digitalisation in the regions was drawn at the Digital Communities Forum held in Lviv at the end of March. The need to establish the position of CDTO (Chief Digital Transformation Officer) in communities was particularly discussed [4].

There are many projects aimed at assisting communities in digitalisation, including financial support provided by separate programmes from USAID, U-LEAD, GIZ and other donor organisations. The E-Governance for Accountability and Participation (EGAP) programme, funded by Switzerland and implemented by the East Europe Foundation in cooperation with the Ministry of Digital Transformation and the Innovabridge Foundation, continues. These programmes provide expert support and mentoring for community representatives involved in digitalisation, helping them to work with existing opportunities, identify needs and develop projects for which funding can be found [5].

For the whole country, the process of council digitalisation opens up the possibility of fast and high-quality optimisation of the Post-War Development Strategy drafting. For each individual community, especially for small and medium-sized ones, this means the possibility of creating a comprehensive development plan for many years, which will become a key document. It also opens the way to unimpeded service delivery to residents, budget optimisation and investment attraction. Digital transformation promotes the creation of regional clusters, innovation parks and hubs, which provides the basis for a greener and more energy-efficient life in all communities across the country, contributing to the development of their economies. In these challenging times, it is important for small communities in particular to see and seize opportunities for development.

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